

Green Human Resource Management and Its Effect on Environmental Performance: The Essential of Green Transition Education

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ABSTRACT

This article explains about the application of green human resource management (HRM) is critical to environmental performance. The researchers employed the documentary approach to writing this review article. First, a random sample of trustworthy and valid sources was taken. Next, using purposive sampling and content analysis were employed on the selected papers. There is, however, a paucity of research examining the connection between green HRM, environmental performance, and green transition education. In addition, findings on critical components of green HRM are somewhat varied from the previous studies. This study shows that it is crucial to identify the key components of green HRM practices to improve environmental performance. Green HRM studies show strong conclusions in improving environmental performance. Environmental performance can be enhanced by using green HRM through key factors. The essentials of green HRM and its critical to environmental performance are discussed. The recommendation for further study should be considered for quantitative statistical analysis. Moreover, qualitative research could give more insight into results such as interviews or focus groups on further study.

Keywords: green, human resource management (HRM), environmental concerns, sustainable, environmental performance

INTRODUCTION

The main practice that should be given priority in an organization is green HRM. Several studies show that environmentally friendly HRM practices improve performance. Green HRM must be carried out correctly if environmental performance is to be successful. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct studies on the strategies used by firms to attain environmental performance through green HRM practices (Usman & Mat, 2021). The organizational citizenship behavior of academic staff toward the environment is influenced by green HRM activities (green competence-building practices, green motivation-enhancing practices, and green employee participation practices), which in turn has an impact on environmental performance (Anwar et al., 2020). Environmental protection has traditionally been regarded as "in the public interest" and external to private life. Environment, business, and management scholars have been

debating how and why businesses should incorporate environmental concerns into their strategies. Numerous businesses have accepted their obligation to protect the environment in the present day. Concerning environmental issues, the business community employs terms that are commonly considered to be associated with business ethics (Málovics et al., 2008). Human resource (HR) plays an important role in organizations adopting a sustainability strategy, whether for business, legal, or values-based reasons. In addition to assisting in the formulation and attainment of environmental and social objectives, the HR department must also strike a balance between these goals and traditional financial performance metrics. The HR function can be a partner in determining what is required or possible in formulating corporate values and sustainability strategy (Cohen, Taylor & Muller-Camen, 2010). Green HRM practices have been shown to improve an organization's environmental performance. Green HRM initiatives can facilitate a green organizational culture and the impact on the environmental performance and sustainable development of a company is crucial. Consequently, it is essential to comprehend and assess the relationship between GHRM practices the enablers of green organizational culture, and a company's environmental performance (Roscoe et al., 2019). Green HRM has emerged as a growing field of conceptual and empirical research within and apart from the broader topic of Sustainable HRM over the past decade. As a result, Green HRM may evolve in the future, posing a variety of COVID-19-related threats to business survival and society. It could influence the growth of Green HRM and lead to its revitalization (Paulet, Holland & Morgan, 2021). Thus, there is an increasing demand for the incorporation of environmental management into Human Resource Management (HRM) practices; these initiatives are known as "Green HRM" (Fayyazi et al., 2015).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Environmental Concerns and Sustainability

The relationship between the natural world and the manufacturing process is growing more and more intimate. Profitability, productivity, and environmental awareness are increasingly seen as key aims of industrial businesses as the new century approaches and moves forward. Environmental concerns cover the problems that manufacturing organizations, in general, and the manufacturing function, in particular, are currently confronting, as well as the future needs of an ecologically sustainable manufacturing firm. There is plenty of potential for practitioners and scholars to advance in the coming millennium even though the focus is on manufacturing strategy and operations, issues pertinent to the total organization and other functions are also relatively novel to most businesses (Sarkis, 2001). Climate and environmental issues adversely affect both financial performance and market value performance. This suggests that businesses may have the propensity to engage in corporate responsibility initiatives solely for self-benefit, which has been shown to harm financial success. Concerns about corporate sustainability are portrayed as a weakening element and a partly mediating component in the relationship between executive pay and financial performance (Kartadjumena & Rodgers, 2019). Multiple motivations and determinants, such as emotional, societal, situational, and demographic factors, impact ecologically sustainable behavior (Nguyen & Johnson, 2020). Sustainability is viewed as a notion in government policy that addresses the conflict between our desires for a better existence and the constraints placed on us by nature. The idea has been reinterpreted over time to embrace three dimensions: social, economic, and environmental. The argument seeks to reframe the meaning as follows: (a) hides the actual conflict between the goals of universal welfare and

environmental preservation; (b) runs the risk of downplaying the significance of the environmental dimension; and (c) separates social from economic aspects, which are identical (Kuhlman & Farrington, 2010). Thus, sustainability relates to many factors such as social, economic, and environmental concerns. In contrast, there is a negative effect between sustainability and the performance of finance and market value.

Green Human Resource Management (Green HRM)

The term "green HRM" refers to the use of human resources management (HRM) techniques to support environmentally sound behavior and raise employee engagement in environmental sustainability concerns. It encompasses considering the objectives and core principles of environmental management while implementing human resources (HR) initiatives that boost productivity and improve environmental performance, both of which are crucial for lowering employees' carbon footprints (Masri & Jaaron, 2017). Currently, the organization has shifted its paradigm, point of view, and level of care for environmental issues, expressing an interest in sustainable development with a focus on environmental performance. With some programs being run to ensure that employees move towards the green organization's function in line with market wishes, it is common for employees in organizations to feel compelled, even with certain incentive drives, to always be aware of the environment's issues (Hutomo et al., 2020). Business leaders, governments, customers, and management academics are becoming increasingly concerned about the issue of environmental sustainability. HRM researchers and practitioners alike have been relatively sluggish to participate in the continuing conversations and debates as these stakeholders battle the difficulties and opportunities posed by a variety of environmental issues. Performance management is related to training, development, learning, pay, benefits, and corporate culture are among the functional HRM approaches. Strategic HRM and environmental management possibilities do exist the vast agenda could start to develop a strong field of green HRM studies if vigorously pursued (Jackson et al., 2011). Through green intellectual capital and pro-environmental behavior, green human resource management practices indirectly contribute to environmental performance. In the field of environment management, human resource management practices incorporate green intellectual capital and pro-environmental behaviors. It contributes explicitly to the vital role of green human resource management practices in enhancing environmental performance (Nisar et al., 2021). Green HRM is the use of HRM strategies to support environmentally behavior among employees to reach sustainability in reducing carbon footprints, such as training, development, learning, pay and benefits, and corporate culture regarding environmental management and its concerns.

Environmental Performance

Green HRM positively influences the environmental sustainability of an organization, which in turn positively influences the social sustainability of an organization. Additionally, corporate social responsibility has a positive effect on employer branding. Confirmation of the mediating effects of corporate environmental sustainability between GHRM and corporate social sustainability. Additionally, a conclusion was reached regarding the relationship between corporate environmental sustainability and employer branding. Sustainability contributes to employer branding. By implementing Green HRM, organizations can gain a competitive advantage, which aids in attracting qualified candidates

(Yasin, Huseynova & Atif, 2022). The environmental performance of the industry is becoming increasingly influenced by global environmental standards. The global environmental standards reflect the various agents involved in their development as well as the specific network architecture by which environmental standards achieve global reach. The new forms of global environmental standards, including firm-based standards and standards initiated by third-party organizations such as nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) and trade associations (Angel, Hamilton & Huber, 2007). Recent years have seen an increase in the recognition of green supply chain management and supply chain environmental management. However, the relationship between greening the supply chain, green innovation, environmental performance, and competitive advantage has received relatively little research attention (Chiou et al., 2011). Thus, environmental performance is related to many factors, such as Green HRM, environmental standards, green supply chain management, etc.

Green Transition Education

Undergraduate students as prospective employees, as opposed to job seekers who may be seeking employment and therefore settle for any job, or current employees who are employed by one organization but are also seeking employment elsewhere. Students have been conducted on organizations' perceived corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices and the role of these perceptions in attracting prospective employees, university students (as prospective employees) perceptions of environmental sustainability, and job search implications. The perceived green HRM effect on the job pursuit intention of students as prospective employees. Employee green behavior, psychological green climate nexus, and highlighting the need for organizations to grasp the increasing interests and concerns of their efforts to attract prospective employees with a propensity to engage in green workplace behavior (Ercantan & Eyupoglu, 2022). The green industrial policy is investigated by examining experiences and barriers to phasing in green technologies, with a particular emphasis on solar and energy efficiency as policy areas. A strategy for sustaining a transition to cleaner and more energy-efficient production processes by combining elements of push and pull policies. Given the priorities for development, imperfect institutions for policymaking and implementation, poorly developed innovation systems, and lock-in issues, green technologies face challenges (Kemp & Never, 2017). Thus, education in schools, universities or any institutions about the green transition is essential for educators' considerations.

METHODOLOGY

Researchers must use their expertise to select the most advantageous sample for their research. This methodology is frequently used in qualitative research. The objective is to acquire extensive understanding. Texts are a common point of departure for qualitative content analysis. The purpose is to condense a large volume of text into a highly organized and concise summary of important findings (Limna et al., 2022 Jaipong et al., 2022). The researchers used the documentary method for this review. In the first step, a random sampling of reliable and valid sources was conducted; in the second step, a content analysis was conducted on the selected papers using purposive sampling. Five databases were consulted for this systematic review, including EBSCO, Google Scholar, Scopus, Web of Science, and ScienceDirect. Inclusion criteria also included studies that were 1) clearly related to green HRM and environmental performance; 2) were published in English, and 3) were reviewed by experts.

The secondary data were investigated and adopting the database was searched using the following keywords: green human resource management (green HRM), environmental concerns, environmental performance, and green transition education was contributed between September 15 and October 18, 2022. Twenty-two articles were analyzed using content analysis out of 21,800 results. The selected research articles were published between 2007 and 2022.

RESULTS

Green HRM should be prioritized above all other practices within an organization. Multiple studies support that eco-friendly human resource management practices enhance environmental performance. If environmental performance is to be successful, green HRM must be executed properly. It is essential to conduct the strategies employed by businesses to achieve environmental performance via green HR practices. The organizational citizenship behavior of academic staff toward the environment is influenced by green HRM activities (green competence-building practices, green motivation-enhancing practices, and green employee participation practices), which impacts environmental performance. Traditionally, environmental protection has been viewed as "in the public interest" and external to private life. Scholars of the environment, business, and management have debated how and why companies should incorporate environmental concerns into their strategies. Today, numerous businesses have accepted their responsibility to protect the environment. Concerning environmental issues, the business community frequently employs terms associated with business ethics. Human resource (HR) plays a significant role in organizations adopting a sustainability strategy for business, legal, or ethical reasons. In addition to assisting in the formulation and attainment of environmental and social objectives, the HR department must strike a balance between these objectives and conventional financial performance metrics. The HR function can be a partner in determining what is necessary or feasible for formulating corporate values and a sustainability strategy. Green HRM practices have been shown to improve the environmental performance of an organization. Green HRM initiatives can foster a green organizational culture, and their impact on a company's environmental performance and sustainable growth is significant. Consequently, it is essential to comprehend and evaluate the relationship between Green HRM practices the enablers of green organizational culture, and the environmental performance of a company. In the past decade, Green HRM has emerged as a growing field of theoretical and empirical research within and apart from the broader topic of Sustainable HRM. Green HRM may therefore evolve in the future, posing numerous COVID-19-related threats to business survival and society. It could affect Green HRM's expansion and lead to its revitalization. Consequently, there is a growing demand for the incorporation of environmental management into Green HRM.

CONCLUSIONS

One of the primary functions of green HRM is measuring employee green job performance. Employees' green performance must be evaluated separately or at least as part of the organization's performance evaluation system. The employee green performance

measurement criteria must be carefully aligned with the organization's environmental performance criteria. Organizations must implement environmental management information systems (EMIS) and environmental audits to sustain good environmental performance. Numerous organizations have implemented environmental management systems that effectively monitor many pollutions, resource usage, energy, and regulatory requirements they face. Incorporating corporate environmental management requires the incorporation of environmental issues, environmental incidents, the acceptance of environmental responsibilities, and the success of communicating environmental concerns and policy into the company's performance evaluation system. Green HRM positively impacts an organization's environmental sustainability, which in turn positively impacts an organization's social sustainability. Additionally, corporate social responsibility benefits employer branding. Confirmation of the mediating effects of environmental sustainability on the relationship between GHRM and social sustainability. In addition, a conclusion was reached concerning the connection between corporate environmental sustainability and employer branding. Sustainability has a positive effect on employer branding. By implementing Green HRM, organizations can gain a competitive advantage, which facilitates the recruitment of qualified candidates. Global environmental standards are increasingly influencing the environmental performance of the industry. The global environmental standards reflect both the various agents involved in their development and the network architecture by which environmental standards achieve global reach. The new forms of global environmental standards, include firm-based standards and standards initiated by third parties such as nongovernmental organizations (NGOs) and trade associations. The acceptance of green supply chain management and supply chain environmental management has increased in recent years. However, relatively little attention has been paid to the relationship between greening the supply chain, green innovation, environmental performance, and competitive advantage. Thus, environmental performance is related to a variety of factors, including green human resource management, environmental standards, green supply chain management, etc.

LIMITATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

It is misleading if disregard the limitations of scoping studies. The amount of data produced should be considered and can lead to challenging decisions regarding when breadth covers all available material superior to depth. The scoping analysis does not address the synthesis issue or the relative weight of evidence supporting the efficacy of any intervention. In consequence, scoping studies offer a narrative or descriptive summary of the available research. Most of these challenges are addressed by systematic review methods that require quality assessment. Thus, reducing the number of included studies and emphasizing data synthesis was employed. Nevertheless, the systematic review process can be very timeconsuming, which is a disadvantage when policymakers require information about existing research evidence quickly. Consider qualitative research, such as interviews and focus group discussions, for insight results rather than quantitative research for relationship explanation.

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